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Angina pectoris from metabolic alkalosis induced by dialysate bicarbonates in a hemodialyzed patient

Running title: Metabolic alkalosis induced angina pectoris during hemodialysis

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Abstract

A hemodialyzed woman developed angina pectoris one hour after the end of the hemodialysis session, without the presence of a hypotensive episode, which resolved with the use of isosorbide dinitrate sublingually. She had diabetes mellitus, arterial hypertension, heart failure and known coronary artery disease (three-vessel disease), for which she was receiving treatment. The electrocardiogram showed a right bundle branch block (paced rhythm). The episodes of angina pectoris recurred in subsequent sessions, always after the session and never the day between sessions. Blood gases (venous sample) were performed during the episode of angina pectoris and elevated bicarbonates were found (alkalemia pattern). The patient reported that she had not consumed animal proteins recently because she did not like them. The bicarbonates of dialysate were then reduced (from 33 to 30 mmol/L) and she was advised to increase her consumption of animal proteins, at which point the angina episodes ceased and the blood gas test (venous sample) after the end of the session did not show the presence of alkalemia (pH 7.334 and bicarbonates 26.5 mmol/L). The case is presented with related bibliographic investigation.

Keywords Hemodialysis, metabolic alkalosis, angina pectoris, dialysate bicarbonates, diet proteins

Case presentation

A 67-year-old woman with coronary artery disease (double bypass in 2002), had diabetes mellitus, hypertension and hypertensive heart disease, heart failure and end-stage renal failure on hemodialysis since September 2017 (primary renal disease was diabetic nephropathy and hypertensive nephrosclerosis). She complained of angina pectoris approximately one hour after the end of the hemodialysis session, which subsided with a sublingual isosorbide dinitrate tablet (Pensordil tabl 5 mg). This occurred several times (once she experienced it twice on the same day) and always on the day of the hemodialysis and never on the day between sessions, without a preceding hypotensive episode during the session and after removal at maximum 500 ml of ultrafiltrate/hour. Coronary angiography performed in January 2021 revealed 100% occlusion of the anterior descending branch, total occlusion of the right coronary artery (two vein grafts occluded) and diffuse atherosclerosis of the circumflex branch (three-vessel disease), with aortic valve stenosis (replacement with Transcatheter Aortic Valve Implantation-TAVI in 2021), as reported, and with a pacemaker (placement in 2021). Electrocardiography revealed right bundle branch block (paced rhythm).

She had a double-lumen hemodialysis catheter in the right jugular vein and was on a predilution online hemodiafiltration (HDF) program, 3 times a week for 4.5 hours/session. She used a polyethersulfone filter (polynephron), 2.5 m² surface area, with a blood pump of 400 ml/min, a substitution volume the 45% of the pump (48.6 L/session) and a dialysate with

bicarbonates 33 mmol/L, acetates 3 mmol/L, potassium 2 or 3 mmol/L, sodium 138 mEq/L and calcium 1.5 mmol/L. The anticoagulant used was bemparin (3,500 IU/session).

The medications she was taking were pantoprazole 1 tabl/day, atorvastatin tabl 20/day, aspirin tabl 100/day, atenolol tabl 25 mg/day, amlodipine tabl 5 mg/day, gabapentin tabl 75 mg/day, cilostazol tabl 100 mg/day, insulin aspart (novomix) 30 IU twice/day and novorapid (aspartate and protamine crystalline insulin) 10 IU/day, sevelamer carbonate tabl 800 (0 in the morning, 3 at noon and 3 in the evening during meals), piracetam syrup 1x3 tablespoons/day, bemparin inj 3,500 IU/on days free dialysis, epoetin-a inj 4,000 IU/session intravenously and paricalcitol inj 3 mcg/session.

Laboratory results in one of the episodes of anginal pain were as follows: hemoglobin (Hb) 10.4 gr%, hematocrit (Hct) 32.7%, white blood cells 6.090/ml (polymorphonuclear 68%, lymphocytes 20%), iron 56 µg/dl, ferritin 409 ng/L, urea 37.1 mmol/L, creatinine 583 mmol/L, sodium 142 mmol/L, potassium 4.7 mmol/L, calcium 2.2 mmol/L, phosphate 0.87 mmol/L, urate 232 mmol/L and parathormone 273 pg/ml.

From the history regarding her diet, which was taken after the finding of the high levels of bicarbonates in the blood before the beginning of dialysis session (26.5 mmol/L) and their much higher value at the end of the session (33 mmol/L) were noted (Fig 1, A, B), it was found that she herself had recently been consuming much less animal proteins (because she chose not to consume these, because she did not like them).

After that the dialysate bicarbonates were reduced to 30 mmol/L. On the first day of the predilution online HDF session with the lower bicarbonate's dialysate, she did not experience anginal pain, as she did during the following sessions. The venous blood gases with these changes in bicarbonates and in diet she had a pH of 7.334 and blood bicarbonate of 26.5 mmol/L (venous sample) after the end of the session, apparently better and free of any symptoms (Fig. 1, C, D).

Fig 1: Patient's blood gases before the start of the dialysis session (A) and one hour after its end (B), with dialyzed bicarbonates 33 mmol/L and patient's blood gases before the start of the dialysis session (C) and one hour after its end (D), with dialyzed bicarbonates 30 mmol/L

Discussion

Metabolic alkalosis does not always cause symptoms and most often those of the disease that caused it are observed. However, manifestations such as muscle spasms (cramps), weakness, headache, confusion, dizziness and seizures may occur mainly caused by changes in electrolytes, such as potassium, calcium and sodium in the serum. Alkalosis also leads to reduced myocardial contractility, arrhythmias, reduced cerebral blood flow, increased neuromuscular excitability and reduced oxygen delivery in tissues, due to the shift of the oxygen of hemoglobin dissociation curve to the left. Also, severe alkalosis is a strong vasoconstrictor, which leads to reduced blood perfusion of the brain, heart and peripheral circulation and to coronary spasm [1,2]. One or both of them it happened in our patient, which was initially dealt with isosorbide dinitrate and finally with a reduction in the dialysate bicarbonates and an increase in the animal protein intake. Overall, alkalosis has a definite effect on the body, resulting in hypoxia and vasoconstriction and the consequences due to them [3].

A study of Bersin et al. showed that the administration of bicarbonate to patients with cardiorespiratory arrest reduces both the oxygen delivery from hemoglobin and its consumption of oxygen by the heart. It was also found that the systemic oxygen consumption and the partial pressure of oxygen in arterial blood (PaO_2) are reduced. The most impressive finding of their study was that the administration of bicarbonates caused a significant reduction in myocardial oxygen consumption. And since the blood supply to the heart was not changed, it is obvious that the reduction in the oxygen delivered was due to a reduction in its delivery from hemoglobin [4]. Quite strangely, the findings of Bersin et al. are generally not observed when bicarbonates are administered to hemodialyzed patients during the session (from the dialysate). In these cases, hypoxemia and circulatory failure are generally absent and respiratory function is normal. That is, these patients can compensate for any effect that bicarbonates may have on tissue oxygen delivery. However, a patient who develops hypoxemia during a bicarbonate dialysis session may have heart disease with limited heart function [5], as did the patient we presenting.

During bicarbonate dialysis, the influx of bicarbonates into the patient depends on the dialyzer and the bicarbonates concentration gradient between the dialysate and the blood. The pH of the blood increases progressively during the session and may be slightly alkaline at the end, depending on the pH before the beginning of the session [6]. As was found in our patient, when her blood bicarbonates were 26.5 mmol/L before the beginning of session and the dialysate bicarbonates were 33 mmol/L, she finished the session with bicarbonates 33 mmol/L, while her initial bicarbonates were 21.7 mmol/L and when the dialysate bicarbonates were 30 mmol/L, she finished the session with bicarbonates 26.5 mmol/L. The usual increase in bicarbonates after a dialysis session with bicarbonates in dialysate is from about 3.5 mmol/L [7] to about 5.0 mmol/L [8]. This means that when bicarbonates are not consumed between sessions due to the lower intake of proteins, which are also the main source of non-volatile acids, it is obvious that it will be easy for the bicarbonates after each session to exceed the 30 mmol/L in the blood and clinical disorders related to alkalemia or alkalosis to arise.

If enough bicarbonates are moved into the patient's blood during dialysis, a state of metabolic alkalosis results and the serum pH rises sharply, with all the inherent dangers of severe alkalemia. Thus, in the immediate post-dialysis period, the patient is expected to be at increased risk for cardiac arrhythmias, angina pectoris, confusion, seizures, and coma [9,10].

Our patient developed angina pectoris one hour after the end of the session, which was attributed to the increase in bicarbonates and pH, due to the patient's non-consumption, because she chose not to eat animal proteins during that period, while the bicarbonates in dialysate remained elevated. Indeed, the reduction of bicarbonates in the dialysate (from 33 to 30 mmol/L) and the restoration of animal proteins to the diet, eliminated the episodes of angina after the end of the session, since her blood bicarbonates from 21.7 mmol/L at the beginning of the session became 26.5 mmol/L at the end of it and the pH from 7.285 at the beginning of the session became 7.334 at the end (Fig. 1). Supporting the relationship between elevated bicarbonates and angina is the fact that the patient never experienced anginal pain between dialysis sessions, when these had already been consumed to neutralize the non-volatile acids produced daily from the protein's metabolism.

Therefore, caution and experience are required when using bicarbonates in patients with cardiac, respiratory, or renal disease. In congestive heart failure, bicarbonates reduce systemic oxygen delivery and myocardial oxygen consumption in these patients, which may lead to transient myocardial ischemia [4]. In addition, there may be multiple concurrent processes that affect the acid-base status among patients with congestive heart failure [11].

In conclusion, it is necessary to check blood gases in hemodialyzed patients to be at least monthly, both for better control and maintenance of the correct acid-base status, and to reveal disorders, such as those of our patient, which would not otherwise be diagnosed.

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